

Gazania rigens Botterblom

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.15 m (height), rhizomatous and forms spreading mats

Distribution:

South Africa and Mozambique: coastal KwaZulu-Natal, Eastern Cape and Western Cape; also widely cultivated and has naturalised beyond its natural distribution.

Importance:

The species is of global importance in horticulture and is a common, ecologically important coastal dune and rock pioneer species on the southern and eastern South African shoreline. Genomic information is vital for future breeding of ornamental *Gazania* cultivars and to unravel the taxonomy, cytology, evolution, genetic diversity and biogeography of *Gazania*.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 25.98 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 32.67 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.02 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 79.8%, Duplicated: 19.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 3 116.53 kilobases

Contig number: 887

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